

Evaluating the Effectiveness of Micro-Teaching Among University Students: A Case Study at Abdulrahman Al-Sumait University

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Abstract

Micro-teaching is a structured, practice-based approach to developing teaching skills through short, focused teaching sessions followed by feedback and reflection. This study examines the impact of micro-teaching on university students' teaching abilities, focusing on classroom management, lesson planning, and assessment skills. Conducted at Abdulrahman Al-Sumait University in Zanzibar, the research follows a cross-sectional quantitative design, utilizing structured questionnaires completed by 118 participants. The results reveal that micro-teaching effectively strengthens teaching competencies, with a majority of participants recognizing its relevance to their professional development. While classroom management and lesson planning showed significant improvement, the study identified a need for further refinement in assessment and evaluation skills. The findings suggest that micro-teaching is a beneficial approach for teacher training and highlight areas for enhancement in instructional preparation.

Keywords: *Micro-teaching, Teaching development, Classroom management, Assessment and Evaluation.*

Suggested citation: Said, A.A., Namanolo, H.S., Mbewe, H.P., & Kiga, S.M. (2025). Evaluating the Effectiveness of Micro-Teaching Among University Students: A Case Study at Abdulrahman Al-Sumait University. *European Journal of Contemporary Education and E-Learning*, 3(2), 207-223. DOI: 10.59324/ejceel.2025.3(2).18

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Introduction

Micro-teaching, introduced in the 1960s at Stanford University (Cavanaugh, 2022; Kallenbach, 1966; Ledger & Fischetti, 2020; Santoveña-Casal et al., 2024), is a focused training method designed to improve teaching skills. Unlike traditional teaching practice, where educators address all aspects of instruction simultaneously, micro-teaching narrows the scope to specific skills, such as questioning, managing time, or delivering clear explanations (El-Koumy, 2022; Pearce, 2021; Salunke, 2023). Trainee teachers deliver short lessons (usually 5–10 minutes) to a small group of peers or students, followed by feedback and reflection (Lakshmi, 2009; Nicol & Boyle, 2003).

Hasan (Hasan et al., 2024) revealed the structured approach that allows teachers to practice, receive constructive feedback, and refine their techniques in a low-pressure environment. However, Zaid and Julius (Julius, 2015; Zaidi, 2015) added that by breaking teaching into smaller and manageable parts, micro-teaching provides an opportunity to build skills gradually and confidently. At its core, micro-teaching simplifies the complex process of teaching into smaller tasks, making it easier to practice and master specific skills (Brown, 1968; Kumar, 2016; Majoni, 2017; Pandey, 2019). Perlberg (Perlberg, 1972) also emphasized that this approach helps teachers focus on one element of teaching at a time, such as engaging students, managing discussions, or asking effective questions. Over time, these skills come together to improve overall teaching performance.

Numerous researches show that micro-teaching is highly effective at building teaching confidence and competence. For instance, Fernández (Fernandez, 2010) found that teachers who participated in micro-teaching sessions improved their ability to communicate effectively, organize their lessons, and interact with students confidently. In another study, MacLeod and Cowieson (MacLeod & Cowieson, 2001) noted that practising in a supportive, controlled setting allowed teachers to gain confidence and better handle classroom dynamics. The practice is especially useful for new teachers, helping them bridge the gap between theory and real-life teaching. By working on specific areas like classroom management or student engagement, teachers become more prepared to face challenges in actual classrooms (Brophy, 1988; Burden, 2020; Davis et al., 2012; Hoy & Weinstein, 2013; Parsons & Taylor, 2011).

One of the most valuable aspects of micro-teaching is the feedback teachers receive after their sessions (Mahmud & Rawshon, 2013; Otsupius, 2014). However, it can come from peers, mentors, or self-reflection; feedback provides insights into what went well and what could be improved (Erdemir & Yeşilçinar, 2021). Kpanja (Kpanja, 2001) demonstrated that detailed feedback led to noticeable improvements in teachers' skills, especially when they applied the suggestions in subsequent sessions. Feedback helps educators identify their strengths, address weaknesses and ensure continuous growth (Göçer, 2016).

Reflection plays a key role in micro-teaching, encouraging teachers to think critically about their methods and make thoughtful adjustments. According to Visser (Visser, 2010) and Bamberger and Schön (Bamberger & Schön, 1983), reflection is essential for professional growth, as it helps teachers connect theoretical knowledge with practical application. Micro-teaching creates the perfect setting for this reflective process, allowing educators to analyze their performance in a focused way.

Micro-teaching is often used to improve specific teaching skills, such as questioning techniques. Research has shown that asking the right kinds of questions can engage students and encourage critical thinking (Nasir, 2021). Micro-teaching gives teachers

the chance to experiment with different questioning strategies and figure out what works best for their students.

Technology has transformed micro-teaching, making it even more effective. Video recording, for example, allows teachers to watch their sessions and notice things they might miss during live teaching (Davis, 1969; Sithole, 2023). Amobi (Amobi, 2005) found that reviewing recordings helped teachers identify subtle aspects of their education, such as body language or pacing. These insights make it easier to refine techniques and improve overall performance. Technology also makes micro-teaching more adaptable, allowing it to be used in online and hybrid learning environments (Santoveña-Casal et al., 2024; Sezaki et al., 2023).

Micro-teaching has become a cornerstone of teacher training programs worldwide, particularly effective for pre-service teachers, who are provided with a safe space to practice before entering real classrooms. Remesh (Remesh, 2013) noted that micro-teaching prepares educators to handle diverse classroom situations and equips them with a range of strategies to engage students. It is also widely used for ongoing professional development, ensuring that even experienced teachers continue to grow and improve (Fisher & Burrell, 2011; Remesh, 2013).

Most of the research on micro-teaching focused on teacher education and professional development. By focusing on specific aspects of teaching, practising them in a structured way, and incorporating feedback, teachers can refine their techniques and improve their overall effectiveness. Therefore, the need to investigate specific skills in micro-teaching is of great importance. To the best of our knowledge, no studies have been undertaken on micro-teaching in Unguja Island, Zanzibar – Tanzania, particularly concerning overall experience and skills development. The absence of this information on the scope of microteaching made this research indispensable.

This study examines the effects of microteaching on the development of teaching competencies, emphasizing its role in enhancing educators' instructional skills and overall teaching effectiveness. By providing opportunities for practice, feedback, and reflection, microteaching enables the refinement of teaching strategies and fosters professional growth. The study explores how these processes improve educators' confidence and their ability to deliver high-quality learning experiences in real classroom settings. The following two research questions guided the study:

1. How do participants perceive the overall experience of the micro-teaching program in their future teaching careers?
2. To what extent has the micro-teaching program improved participant's teaching skills?

The rest part of this study is structured as follows: in Section 2. we introduce the methodology for research design and data collection. The analysis and discussion of the obtained results are presented in Section 3, while the conclusion and summary of this work appear in Section 4.

Methodology

Research Design

This study employed a cross-sectional quantitative research design using a structured questionnaire to gather data. This design was selected for its suitability in collecting large-scale data efficiently and providing robust statistical analyses. The survey aimed

to explore the overall experience and teaching skills they get from micro-teaching programs among a defined population.

Population and Sampling

The target population consisted of university students. A total of 118 participants were selected from four different microteaching groups at Abdulrahman Al-Sumait University by stratified random sampling to ensure adequate representation of their respective groups to observe the overall experience and teaching skills they get from microteaching. All 118 participants completed the questionnaire, yielding a 100% response rate. This high response rate minimized non-response bias and ensured comprehensive data representation (Cheung et al., 2017; Hendra & Hill, 2019). This method was deemed suitable to enhance the standard of this study (Creswell et al., 2014; Moh'd et al., 2021).

Instrumentation

A structured questionnaire was developed as the primary data collection tool. The questionnaire was composed of three sections. The first section covered demographic information aimed at capturing data on students' age, gender, study major (BA with education/BSc with education) and other relevant factors. The second and third sections covered the overall experience and skills development in this study, respectively. Questions were designed based on established scales and prior literature to ensure validity and reliability. The instrument included closed-ended items using Likert scales ranked from 1 to 5 in the range of not at all to extremely effective for skills development part, very poor to excellent in overall experience, and other multiple-choice questions to capture quantitative data adopted from (Moh'd et al., 2021) respectively. Additionally, a few open-ended questions were included to allow participants to provide qualitative insights.

The questionnaire underwent rigorous pre-testing and validation. Expert reviews were conducted to ensure content and construct validity, and a pilot study was performed to test clarity and reliability. Cronbach's alpha was used to assess the internal consistency of the questionnaire, achieving a value of 0.827, which indicates acceptable reliability (Tavakol & Dennick, 2011).

Data Collection Procedure

Data were collected at the conclusion of the micro-teaching program to capture participants' immediate reflections and insight. Participants were briefed on the objectives of the study and assured of the anonymity and confidentiality of their responses. The questionnaire was administered in a controlled setting, ensuring uniformity in data collection.

Data Analysis

Quantitative data were analyzed using descriptive statistics, including means, variance and standard deviations, to summarize participant responses. The analysis focused on the "Overall Experience" and "Skill Development" sections to assess the program's effectiveness in these areas. Open-ended responses were analyzed qualitatively using thematic analysis. Responses were coded into themes to identify common patterns and unique insights that provided context and depth to the quantitative findings. Themes such as "increased confidence" and "practical application of skills" emerged as prominent areas of discussion.

Ethical Considerations

The study adhered to ethical principles outlined by specific ethical guidelines (Goodyear et al., 2007; Grol, 1990). Participation was voluntary, and informed consent was secured from all participants before they proceeded with the survey. Furthermore, they were provided with informed consent and were assured of their right to withdraw from the study at any time. Measures were implemented to maintain confidentiality, including anonymization of responses.

Results and discussion

Survey Overview and Statistical Analysis of the Micro-Teaching Program

The quantitative analysis of the questionnaire was done using descriptive statistics based on different components, which are overall experience and skills development. In this paper, the data were collected from 118 respondents, allowing for a substantial sample size to draw meaningful conclusions. The mean, variance, and standard deviation were identified for each component based on the following formulae.

$$\text{Mean } (\mu) = \frac{\sum(x_i \cdot f_i)}{N} \quad (1)$$

Where x_i The value of the category is, f_i Is the frequency of that category, and N is the total number of responses.

$$\text{Variance } (\sigma^2) = \frac{\sum f_i(x_i - \mu)^2}{N} \quad (2)$$

$$\text{Standard Deviation } (\sigma) = \sqrt{\sigma^2} \quad (3)$$

Overall Experience

In this section, the study is in-depth focused on the contribution of the micro-teaching program and the experience perceived by the students during that process. The results for three items, overall satisfaction, engagement level and perceived relevance, were present. The data distribution and percentage calculations were also presented to ensure clarity.

How satisfied are you with the micro-teaching program?

Participants' satisfaction was assessed using a structured rating scale ranging from "Very Poor" to "Excellent," providing a nuanced understanding of their perceptions. The analysis revealed a predominantly favourable response, with 53.4% of participants rating their satisfaction as "Good" and 39.8% as "Excellent." Notably, only a small fraction of the cohort provided less favourable evaluations, with 5.1% selecting "Fair" and 1.7% indicating "Very Poor," while no participants rated the satisfaction as "Poor." These results, as illustrated in Figure 1, emphasize the overwhelmingly positive response, reflecting a high level of satisfaction among participants and reinforcing the effectiveness of the intervention or program under evaluation. This distribution

highlights the robustness of the outcomes and their potential implications for broader applications.

Figure 1. Participants Overall Satisfaction with the Micro-Teaching Program

These findings from Figure 1 imply a strong positive skew in the data, indicative of high overall satisfaction with the program. The lack of responses in the "Poor" category further reinforces the quality and appeal of the micro-teaching experience, suggesting that the program effectively meets or surpasses participant satisfaction, with opportunities for minor improvements noted by a few who rated it as "Fair." The central tendency of responses is heavily weighted toward favourable ratings, supporting the program's efficacy as an instructional tool for future educators.

How relevant do you think the micro-teaching program is to your future teaching career?

The analysis of Participants assessed the program's relevance to their career development, with responses ranging from "Not at all relevant" to "Extremely relevant". The observation illustrated in Figure 2 shows an overwhelming 85.6% rated the program as either "Very relevant" (46.6%) or "Extremely relevant" (39.0%), highlighting the perceived applicability of the program to real-world teaching roles. However, only 11.9% considered it "Moderately relevant," while 2.5% rated it as either "Not at all relevant" or "Slightly relevant."

Figure 2. Perceived Relevance of the Micro-Teaching Program to Future Teaching Careers

These results evidently suggest that the program's curriculum is well-aligned with the skills and competencies required for a teaching career, which may include practical teaching techniques, classroom management strategies, and curriculum planning. The

positive skew toward high relevance indicates that participants likely view this program as a valuable investment in their professional development. This is consistent with constructivist learning theory, which posits that learners find value in content that connects directly to their future professional contexts (Applefield et al., 2000; Fosnot, 2013; Wilson, 1996).

How engaging were the micro-teaching sessions?

Respondents rated session engagement across five levels, from *Not at all engaging* to *Extremely engaging*. The results in Figure 3 reveal that nearly 80% of participants found the sessions highly engaging, with 49.2% describing them as "Very engaging" and 30.5% as "Extremely engaging." A minority of responses fell in the lower engagement categories, with 14.4% marking "Moderately engaging" and only 5.9% rating the sessions as either "Not at all engaging" or "Slightly engaging."

Figure 3. Engagement Level in the Micro-Teaching Sessions

The high level of engagement suggests that the session incorporated elements that aligned well with effective pedagogical practices, potentially including interactive activities, collaborative tasks, or real-world application of teaching concepts. This positive distribution of engagement levels underscores the program's ability to capture participant interest, a critical factor in adult learning theories that emphasize engagement as essential for effective knowledge transfer and retention, as reported by (Noe et al., 2010).

The statistical summary of participant responses under the overall experience of the micro-teaching program that depicts the discussion of Figures 1, 2 and 3 is shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Statistical Summary of Participant Responses on Overall Experience, Engagement, and Career Relevance of the Micro-Teaching Program

Items	Mean	Variance	Standard deviation
Overall Satisfaction	4.29	0.28	0.51
Engagement Level	4.10	0.49	0.70
Relevance to Carrer	4.26	0.34	0.58

The Quantitative Study of participants' responses in Table 1 on the first raw indicates a consistently preeminent level of satisfaction and engagement with the micro-teaching

program. The average rating for overall satisfaction was 4.2 on a 5-point scale, with a low variance of 0.28 and a standard deviation of 0.53, indicating a strong central trend towards good experiences and limited variability across replies. The values indicate a strong agreement on the program's quality, demonstrating its efficacy in fulfilling participant expectations.

The engagement levels from the second row in Table 1 correspondingly exhibited a positive distribution, with an average of 4.1 and a standard deviation of 0.7. The comparatively low standard deviation emphasizes a consistent perception of session engagement throughout the sample group. The focused response pattern indicates that the program's design effectively integrates broadly engaging features, perhaps owing to interactive and pedagogically linked teaching approaches.

Table 1 in the third row indicates the relevance to future teaching careers was rated highly, with an average of 4.3, variation of 0.34, and standard deviation of 0.58. The limited variation in replies highlights the perceived relevance of the program's content to participants' professional growth. The high relevance ratings, together with low dispersion, indicate that the micro-teaching program proficiently targets core competencies and pedagogical methods deemed beneficial by participants for their prospective future roles.

The statistical metrics highlight the program's strength in promoting an engaging learning environment and aligning with the professional goals of future educators. The consistently high evaluations in satisfaction, engagement, and relevance reveal the program's overall effectiveness, while the low variability confirms its widespread appeal and flexibility to participant requirements.

Professional Development

Teacher professional development programs play a critical role in enhancing instructional practices and improving student outcomes. This study evaluates the effectiveness of a program designed to develop three key competencies: lesson planning skills, classroom management skills, and assessment and evaluation skills. However, there were notable differences in the degree of effectiveness reported for each competency. Additionally, these findings delve into an in-depth discussion of these key findings, contextualizing them within the broader literature on teacher training and professional development.

Classroom Management Skills: The Program's Greatest Strength

The most striking finding of this study is the exceptionally high level of satisfaction reported by participants regarding the program's impact on classroom management skills. A remarkable 83.82% of respondents rated the program as Very or Extremely Effective in this domain. This suggests that the strategies, resources, and techniques provided during the program were particularly well-suited to address the challenges that educators face in managing classroom dynamics. This explanation is nailed with the fact that effective classroom management, from a pedagogical perspective, is foundational in creating a conducive learning environment (Marzano & Marzano, 2003). Therefore, the program's success in this area may be attributed to its focus on evidence-based practices such as proactive behaviour management, clear communication of expectations, and the use of structured routines. These elements are known to reduce disruptive behaviours and enhance student engagement (Evertson & Weinstein, 2006).

In having a critical analysis, Figure 4 presents the percentage distribution of response management skills across the five effective levels. However, the dominance of the "very effective" and "Extremely effective" categories highlights the effectiveness of the micro-teaching program for student teachers. Moreover, in this figure, the absence of any "Not Effective" responses indicates that even participants who may have initially struggled with classroom management found value in the program's offerings.

Figure 4. Percentage Distribution of Responses for Classroom Management Skills

This finding aligns with previous research highlighting the importance of targeted professional development in classroom management. For instance, studies have shown that teachers who receive focused training in this area report increased confidence and improved student outcomes (Simonsen et al., 2008). The study extends this body of literature by demonstrating the efficiency of a comprehensive program that integrates classroom management strategies with other competencies, emphasizing the interconnected nature of teaching skills.

Lesson planning skills: Strong but room for Growth

The program also demonstrated strong effectiveness in enhancing lesson planning skills, with 75.42% of participants rating it a Very or Extremely Effective, as shown in Figure 5. This result reflects the program's ability to provide educators with practical tools and frameworks for designing coherent, standards-aligned lessons. In alignment with this, it has to be noted that Effective lesson planning is a cornerstone of instructional quality, as it ensures that learning objectives are clearly defined and aligned with assessment criteria (Wiggins & McTighe, 2005). However, the slightly lower proportion of participants reporting Very or Extremely Effective outcomes in this domain compared to classroom management (75.42% vs. 83.82%) suggests that some educators may require additional support in translating theoretical knowledge into practice. This could be due to the complexity of balancing multiple factors, such as differentiated instruction, technology integration, and formative assessment within a single lesson plan. Future iterations of the program might benefit from incorporating

more hands-on activities, peer collaboration, and feedback mechanisms to address these challenges.

Figure5. Lesson Planning Skills

Moreover, the relatively higher percentage of participants (19.49%) reporting Moderate Effectiveness in lesson planning highlights the variability in individual needs and prior experiences among educators. Research has shown that novice teachers often struggle more with lesson planning than experienced educators, suggesting that differentiated training approaches may be necessary to cater to diverse learner profiles (Darling-Hammond, 2000; Martin & Mulvihill, 2017).

Assessment and Evaluation Skills: A Domain Requirement Enhanced Focus

While the program was effective in developing assessment and evaluation skills, the results indicate that this domain presents the greatest opportunity for improvement. However, according to Figure 6, only 64.41% of participants rated the program as Very or Extremely Effective, which is notably lower than the ratings for classroom management and lesson planning. Additionally, a relatively higher proportion, 29.6% of participants, reported Moderate Effectiveness, suggesting that many educators found the content challenging or insufficiently tailored to their needs. In alignment with this, it has to be noted that assessment literacy is a complex and multifaceted competency that requires teachers to understand both the technical aspects of assessment design and the pedagogical implications of using assessments to inform instruction (Popham, 2011). The lower ratings in this domain may reflect the inherent difficulty of mastering these skills, as well as the need for more extensive and sustained professional development in this area.

Research has consistently shown that teachers often lack confidence in designing valid and reliable assessments, particularly when it comes to aligning assessments with learning objectives and standards (Stiggins et al., 2004). To address this gap, future programs could incorporate advanced modules on topics such as item writing, rubric development, and data analysis. Additionally, providing opportunities for ongoing

support through coaching, mentoring, or collaborative inquiry groups could help educators deepen their understanding and application of assessment practices.

Figure 6. Assessment and Evaluation Skills

Comparative Analysis and Broader Implication

When comparing the three competencies evaluated in this study, as shown in Figure 7, it becomes evident that the program's effectiveness varies depending on the specific skill being addressed. This variation highlights the need for a nuanced approach to teacher professional development. It recognizes that different competencies may require distinct strategies and levels of support of additional knowledge and skills to be addressed to prospective teachers in building their competency level in the respective area.

Figure 7. Overall Effectiveness Across Competencies

Additionally, by referring to Figure 8, which compares the three levels of skills for moderate effectiveness, the data suggests that more participants feel moderately effective in assessment and evaluation compared to Lesson Planning and Classroom Management. Fewer participants report moderate effectiveness in Classroom Management, which could mean that more teachers either feel very effective or less effective in this area rather than moderately effective. The results could imply areas where further support or training may be needed, especially if the goal is to move teachers from moderate to high effectiveness.

Figure 8. The proportion of Participants Reporting Moderate Effectiveness

Moreover, in this study, the rate of not effective and slightly effective, as shown in Figure 9, is not of interest. This result evidently shows that there are very low numbers of students rating any of the categories at these low levels. This indicates a strong positive baseline and a general absence of serious concerns about the teachers' abilities in these areas. In essence, the "Not Effective" and "Slightly Effective" categories in this Figure act as a confirmation of generally positive perception rather than indicating significant areas of concern.

Figure 9. Comparison of Effective Ratings across Competence

Conclusion

The Micro-teaching program findings of this study provide strong evidence that the teacher professional development program was highly effective in significantly enhancing participants' skills, particularly in the areas of classroom management and lesson planning. The program's success in these areas suggests that targeted, competency-based training can have a direct and positive impact on teachers' ability to manage classrooms effectively and design well-structured, engaging lessons.

However, the study also revealed that while the program achieved moderate success in improving participants' skills in assessment and evaluation, the results in these areas were not as striking. Despite showing promise, the relatively lower ratings for assessment and evaluation indicate a gap that needs to be addressed in future iterations of the program. Effective assessment and evaluation skills are critical for teachers to monitor student progress and adapt their teaching strategies accordingly, ensuring that all students can succeed.

These findings underscore the importance of creating comprehensive professional development programs that focus not only on the most immediate needs of teachers, like classroom management, but also on the more complex, long-term skills required for student assessment and academic evaluation. As the educational landscape continues to evolve, teacher training programs must remain dynamic and responsive to these changes. By enhancing the focus on assessment and evaluation while continuing to strengthen other competencies, educators will be better equipped to meet the increasingly diverse and complex needs of modern classrooms.

In conclusion, this study highlights the importance of ongoing refinement and adaptation in teacher professional development programs. As these programs evolve to meet the changing demands of the educational field, they will play an integral role in supporting educators' growth and ultimately improving the overall quality of education.

Acknowledgements

The authors acknowledge the support from Abdulrahman Al-Sumait University.

Data Availability Statement

All data can be obtained from the corresponding author upon request.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest regarding the publication of this paper.

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